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M.F. ORLOV'S THEORY OF PUBLIC CREDIT AND MODERN TIMES

The historical experience of domestic economic science, accumulated over the centuries, is of significant theoretical and practical interest in modern conditions, since many modern problems, including the development of financial and credit relations, were posed and solved in the past. In connection with the purpose of the study, the analysis of the scientific contribution of M.F. Orlov in the development of the problem of public credit and its assessment in the context of modernity. Historical-retrospective, historical-genetic, programmatic-target and structural-functional analysis methods were used in the work. Research based on the writings of M.F. Orlov, as well as on the works of other authors, published at different times and covering specific aspects of his social and economic views. Presented conclusions M.F. Orlov on the implementation of the state credit policy, the theory and practice of lending, the problems of internal and external debt, the ratio of state and private credit. Aspects such as methods and conditions of public credit organization, credit ratio and taxation are highlighted. The conclusion was formulated that despite the contradictory nature of the theory M.F. Orlov on state credit it has retained its relevance in the context of setting and solving the problem of overcoming social and economic inequality in modern conditions and increasing the overall effectiveness of financial and credit policy.

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